

TÉLÉCOM PARIS

IA311 - Project IA

**A DEEP LEARNING APPROACH TO PREDICT SOCIOECONOMIC INDICATORS
IN VALE DO RIBEIRA FROM SATELLITE IMAGERY**

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1. Introduction

Data on key measures of socioeconomic development can be a powerful tool to assist government policies decisions. However, reliable data on such measures at the local level is still lacking in many parts of the world, especially in developing countries. This mainly occurs due to the difficulties of scaling up traditional data collection efforts, such as government surveys, which can be expensive, time-consuming, and overlook hard-to-reach areas.

In the Brazilian context, the main census institute is known as IBGE (Brazilian Institute of Geography and Statistics) and the data collection is done usually at 10-year intervals. This periodicity produces a data gap that prejudices the interpretability of the collection results, since they may not reflect the Brazilian reality in real-time. The goal of this project is to develop an inexpensive and scalable deep learning method for estimating socioeconomic indicators to fill this data gap using satellite imagery. This is very promising due to the low consumption of resources and the great availability of satellite images, allowing to cover larger and more remote areas and making the process automated and more efficient, without the necessity of on-site collection.

To this end, the project aims to replicate the work done by Yeh et al. (2020) [1] in the Brazilian scenario, more specifically, the region Vale do Ribeira will be used as a case study. Yeh et al. uses deep neural networks to predict socioeconomic criteria in African countries, based on satellite images of their territories.

This work is being developed as part of the PARSEC¹ project, in which one of its objectives is to promote adequate monitoring of the environmental situation in the various biomes of Brazil and to analyze the socioeconomic influence of protected areas on the cities surrounding them.

2. Literature review

As mentioned earlier, this project is a replication of the article of Yeh et al. [1] applied to the Brazilian scenario, using the Vale do Ribeira region as a case study. Another relevant research is the one developed by Triñanes et al. [2], which yields results from another deep learning approach that was used with the same objective of this research, predicting socioeconomic data in the Vale do Ribeira region.

¹ PARSEC: composed by a worldwide group of researchers that have the goal of improving research outcomes, data sharing, and data reuse and also to help pioneer new scientific and data science technologies aimed at improving both the management and conservation of global biodiversity (<https://parsecproject.org/sample-page/>).

Those articles were used as the main consulting source for the reproduction of this work and are further detailed below.

2.1 Yeh, C. et al. Using publicly available satellite imagery and deep learning to understand economic well-being in Africa (2020)

In this article, public satellite imagery was used to train a combined deep learning model to estimate socioeconomic conditions over space and time in several regions of sub-Saharan Africa.

For this purpose, two ResNet-18 [8] models were trained separately on multispectral daytime imagery from 30m/pixel Landsat and <1 km/pixel nighttime lights imagery. Then, the final layers of the separate models were concatenated in a final fully connected layer and a ridge regression was used to fine-tune the model.

To gather the dataset, the authors assembled data on asset wealth using the Demographic and Health Surveys (DHS) [9] conducted between the years 2009 and 2016, as well as an independent smaller set of household level panel data, the Living Standards Measurement Surveys (LSMS) [10]. With this, the authors were able to establish the villages of the African countries as 'clusters'. Then, Landsat surface reflectance and nightlights images centered on each cluster location were obtained with 30m/pixel resolution, spanning 6.72km on each side.

The model was able to explain on average 70% ($R^2 = 0.7$) of the variation in ground-based wealth measurements, with the results never below 50% ($R^2 = 0.5$). For the predictive performance over time, the authors used different approaches, with the most predictive one yielding an $R^2 = 0.35$.

Note that for the adaptation of the model to the Brazilian scenario, the studies were focused on replicating only the performance over space, since the dataset used is not of multiple years.

2.2 Triñanes et al. Application of a deep learning algorithm for predicting socioeconomic data through satellite images in the Vale do Ribeira. (2020)

This article adapted the article of Jean et al. [3] to predict socioeconomic data for the Brazilian scenario, using the Vale do Ribeira region as a case study. In this approach, a VGG11 [11] model is fine-tuned to estimate nighttime light intensity at various locations given the corresponding daytime satellite images. After extracting the features of the daytime satellite imagery by discarding the nighttime light classification layer, those features are used to train ridge regression models that can estimate cluster-level expenditures or assets.

The socioeconomic data was calculated using the IBGE census of 2010 and the methodology of Abreu et al. [5]. In this model, 10km x 10km clusters were generated around the center point of each sector. For each cluster at least 10 satellite images were obtained.

Even though the methodology that is used in Triñanes et al. [2] and the one that is developed in this report are different, the socioeconomic data studied is the same (dimensions of the Human Development Index, as explained in section 5.1) and, therefore, the performance of the model developed by Triñanes et al. can be used as a benchmark for comparison.

3. Case Study: Vale do Ribeira

Vale do Ribeira (VR) was chosen as a case study due to its data availability and its ecological and economic importance. It is located in the southern region of Brazil, encompassing the states of Paraná and São Paulo. With 28,306 km², it has 30 municipalities and it is the largest continuous area of preserved Atlantic Forest in Brazil, being declared as a Natural Heritage of Humanity by UNESCO (United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization) in 1999.

Finally, even though it has a high economic development, this area is considered economically poor and has the lowest human development index in the state of São Paulo [4], being very interesting to study.

Figure 1: Vale do Ribeira and its municipalities. Source: Machicao et al. [14]

Vale do Ribeira has 954 census sectors, which is defined as a group of approximately 300 households within a defined area. However, IBGE only published the census data related to 880 sectors due to data privacy issues (sectors with low population density or with few answers were removed), therefore only 880 sectors were considered valid for this study. For better visualization, in Figure 2 the valid census sectors as well as the conservation units that surround/cover Vale do Ribeira are shown. Furthermore, in Table 1 is shown the number of valid census sectors by state and municipality in alphabetical order.

Figure 2: Conservation units surrounding Vale do Ribeira. The regions colored in blue represent the valid sectors, while the conservation units (also called protected areas) that surround/cover Vale do Ribeira are colored in rouse. Source: Author's Compilation

Table 1. Statistics of census sectors, municipalities and states in the Vale do Ribeira.

State	Municipality	Num. census sectors	State	Municipality	Num. census sectors
PR	Adrianópolis	21	SP	Itariri	61
SP	Apiaí	55	SP	Itaóca	9
SP	Barra Do Chapéu	11	SP	Jacupiranga	26
SP	Barra Do Turvo	14	SP	Juquitiba	54
PR	Bocaiúva Do Sul	23	SP	Juquiá	36
SP	Cajati	38	SP	Miracatu	48
SP	Cananéia	27	SP	Pariquera-açu	27
PR	Cerro Azul	42	SP	Pedro De Toledo	17
PR	Doutor Ulysses	13	SP	Registro	69
SP	Eldorado	30	SP	Ribeira	8

SP	Iguape	60	PR	Rio Branco Do Sul	58
SP	Ilha Comprida	28	SP	Sete Barras	26
SP	Iporanga	19	SP	São Lourenço Da Serra	27
PR	Itaperuçu	34	SP	Tapiraí	15
SP	Itapirapuã Paulista	9	PR	Tunas Do Paraná	12

Source: Author's compilation

4. Overall Workflow

The workflow used in this project to replicate the work of Yeh et al. [1] was divided in four steps (Figure 3).

Step 1: Satellite imagery and IBGE census data acquisition and aggregation.

Step 2: feature extraction, in which two pretrained Resnet18 networks models were modified to adapt multi-band satellite imagery and used to extract the feature vectors of the images. The loss function used was mean squared error (MSE). The training followed a 5-fold cross-validation.

Step 3: ridge regression, in which the feature vectors were fed to the fully connected layer of the Resnet18. The loss function used was mean squared error. The training followed a leave-one-group-out cross-validation.

Step 4: results analysis, in which performance metrics such as the coefficient of determination (R^2) were calculated and graphs were drawn to better analyze the results.

Figure 3: Workflow diagram. Source: Author's compilation.

5. Data Acquisition

5.1 Socioeconomic Indicators

The socioeconomic proxies utilized in the model were obtained using data gathered from IBGE from the 2010 census, the latest census available.

The IBGE and Atlas Brazil [6] publish a municipal Human Development Index (HDI) every decade based on the census data and other surveys. The HDI is a statistical index composed of income, longevity, and education indicators. It was developed and compiled by the United Nations to measure the various levels of social and economic development of countries. In this work, we will focus only on the income indicator of this index. To construct a income index in the granularity of the census sectors, the methodology proposed by Abreu et al. [5], which promotes a methodological proposal for spatial calculation and analysis of the intra-urban Human Development Index of a Brazilian census sector, was adapted to the Vale do Ribeira's Region. Note that this adaptation had already been done by the PARSEC group in a previous study and its script can be found here: <https://github.com/PARSECworld/streetsValeRibeira/blob/main/IDHMs/IDHMs.ipynb>. In this

script the indicators are divided in quintiles. I adapted the code to export the indicators with their continuous values in [0, 1], where 0 stands for the lowest income and 1 the highest one.

Below is described the overview of the calculations made for the income index. More details can be found in Abreu et al. [5].

$$\text{HDI-Income} = (\text{Ln RPC} - \text{Ln RMIN}) / (\text{Ln RMAX} - \text{Ln RMIN})$$

- RPC is the income per capita of a census sector, calculated as the division of the total nominal monthly income for responsible householders by the total resident population in the census sector.
- RMIN is the minimum income reference and RMAX is the maximum income reference, with values R\$ 8.00 and R\$ 4033.00, respectively, according to Atlas Brazil [6].

5.2 Satellite Imagery

The satellite imagery chosen were multispectral daytime imagery from 30m/pixel Landsat and <1 km/pixel nighttime lights imagery. The motivation for choosing nighttime lights imagery was that earlier studies demonstrated that they can serve as an indicator of economic activities at night [12] and, when this indicator is compared across regions and over time, it can be used to measure economic performance. Regarding the choice of daytime imagery, earlier works demonstrated that high-resolution (<1 m/pixel) imagery from private-sector providers can be used to measure spatial variation in local economic outcomes in several developing and middle-income countries. Nevertheless, high-resolution imagery remains very expensive nowadays, so Yeh et al. [1] decided to focus on more coarser public imagery that can be found for free.

5.2.1 Google Earth Engine

The framework Google Earth Engine (GEE) [7] was used for the collection of the satellite imagery. GEE is a cloud-based geospatial analysis platform that enables users to visualize and analyze satellite images of our planet, its public data archive includes more than forty years of historical imagery and scientific datasets, being free for academic and research uses.

5.2.2 Methodology

The methodology adopted by Yeh et al. focuses on obtaining the Landsat surface reflectance and nightlights images centered on each cluster location. The same is done in this project, in which the clusters are the census sectors of the Vale do Ribeira's municipalities. Figure 4 exemplifies that procedure, representing the central coordinates of the images acquired for one sample municipality, Doutor Ulysses, PR.

Figure 4: Example of central coordinates used to acquire satellite images for the municipality of Doutor Ulysses. The census sectors are delimited by a black line and represented with different tones of blue and the red points symbolize the centroid points for each census sector. The y-axis of the map indicates the latitude and the x-axis the longitude.

Source: Author's compilation.

Following the methodology of Yeh et al., it was obtained a 3-year median composite for the Landsat surface reflectance. This composite was created by taking the median of each cloud free pixel available during the period of 3 years, which in this case is 2009 to 2011, since the Brazilian census survey was done in 2010. As the author's describe in their original paper, the motivation for using three-year composites was two-fold. First, multi-year median compositing has seen success in similar applications as a method to gather clear satellite imagery. Second, the outcome we are trying to predict tends to evolve slowly over time (income), and we similarly wanted the inputs to not be distorted by seasonal or short-run variation.

The Landsat surface reflectance imagery was captured by the Landsat 5 and Landsat 7 satellites, with seven bands which we refer to as the multispectral (MS) bands: RED, GREEN, BLUE, NIR (Near Infrared), SWIR1 (Shortwave Infrared 1), SWIR2 (Shortwave Infrared 2), and TEMP1 (Thermal), all with a spatial resolution of 30 m/pixel. Those are all the surface reflectance bands available for both the satellites in question. See Table 2 for a description of the bands mentioned.

Table 2. Description of Landsat 5 and 7 surface reflectance bands.

Name	Units	Wavelength	Description
B1		0.45-0.52 μm	Band 1 (blue) surface reflectance
B2		0.52-0.60 μm	Band 2 (green) surface reflectance
B3		0.63-0.69 μm	Band 3 (red) surface reflectance
B4		0.77-0.90 μm	Band 4 (near infrared) surface reflectance
B5		1.55-1.75 μm	Band 5 (shortwave infrared 1) surface reflectance
B6	Kelvin	10.40-12.50 μm	Band 6 surface temperature.
B7		2.08-2.35 μm	Band 7 (shortwave infrared 2) surface reflectance

Source: https://developers.google.com/earth-engine/datasets/catalog/LANDSAT_LT05_C01_T1_SR#bands

Note that in the original paper, Landsat 8 was also used since images taken from these satellites have been available since 2013 and in the original study the surveys were from several years (2009 to 2017). This satellite contains more bands than the others, nevertheless, the bands chosen are the same for consistency.

For comparability, it was also created 3-year median composites for the nightlights imagery (NL). The main difference here is that the authors used DMSP and VIIRS because no single satellite captured nightlights for all that period. In the case of this work, only DMSP imagery was used, since the first year of availability of the VIIRS dataset at GEE is 2014. Note that the nightlight imagery is much more coarse than the daytime imagery we acquired, with a resolution of 927.67 meters. The images are resized using nearest-neighbor resampling to cover the same spatial area as the Landsat images, this is done by default by GEE during reprojection.

Finally, both MS and NL images were processed in and exported from GEE in 255×255 tiles, with a 30m/pixel resolution, then at the training stage center-cropped to 224×224 (the input size of the convolutional neural network architecture), spanning 6.72 km on each side (30 m Landsat pixel size \times 224px). Note that the reason why 255×255 tiles are used is to have the flexibility of using ‘random crops’ as a form of data augmentation.

5.3 Data Aggregation

The files were exported as TFRecords, a simple format for storing a sequence of binary records, including all the bands (MS + NL) but as well other relevant data such as the values of the socioeconomic data labels. Inspecting those records, I was able to obtain Figure 5, in which it is possible to see the bands plotted for one census sector of the municipality of Doutor Ulysses. Note that each band highlights different aspects of the image, being useful to identify different features. The red, blue and green (RGB) all together create a true color band combination. The

goal of displaying that combination in the figure was to create a visual map of the area that is intuitive for the human eye.

Figure 5: Bands plotted for the census sector of the municipality of Doutor Ulysses, centered at the coordinates (24,567837° S, 49.419754° W). The color map refers to the normalized pixel values. Source: Author's compilation.

6. Deep Learning Methodology

The goal of this project is to train a convolutional neural network (CNN) to predict socioeconomic indicators using a combined model that incorporates both multispectral daytime imagery and nighttime lights in a deep learning model trained end-to-end. For this purpose, two ResNet-18 models were modified and trained separately on the Landsat bands and nightlights bands. Then, the final layers of the separate models were joined in a final fully connected layer and ridge-regression models were trained.

6.1 ResNet-18 Modifications

Residual Network (ResNet) is a convolution neural network that was introduced in 2015 by Kaiming He et Al. [8], being the winner of the ILSVRC Imagenet 2015 competition and becoming quite popular for image recognition and classification tasks because of its ability to solve the vanishing gradient problem.

As in the original article, the CNN models were trained using the ResNet-18 architecture with preactivation [8]. Since the ResNet, as most existing CNN models, is designed to work with 3-channel RGB images, the first convolutional layer was modified to accommodate multi-band satellite imagery. This is actually simple to visualize, basically when using C channels, where C is the number of channels, the filters of the first convolutional layer will have depth of C instead of 3, which means that instead of $[F, F, 3, 64]$, the dimensions of the weights become $[F, F, C, 64]$, where F is the filter size of the first convolution layer.

As in the original paper, the weight of the layers were initialized with the pre-trained value of ImageNet [13] with exception of the first and last layers. In the first layer, the weights for the RGB bands are also initialized as the pre-trained values but the weights for the non-RGB bands are initialized as the average of the weights from the RGB channels and normalized by a factor of $3/C$. For the final layer, the weights are initialized randomly from a standard normal distribution truncated at ± 2 . Finally, for the models trained only on the nightlights bands, the first layer weights were initialized randomly using He's initialization [8] (Gaussian with same overall mean and standard deviation as the RGB channels).

Furthermore, the fully connected layer of the CNN is adapted to do a regression instead of a classification. See Figure 6 for an overall representation of the ResNet18 modified.

ResNet18 Pre Activation Modified

Figure 6: ResNet18 with preactivation basic structure modified. Basically, the ResNet consists in a 7x7 convolution, followed by a batch normalization, a ReLU activation function and a max pooling; 8 residual blocks that repeat itself through the architecture following the same overall pattern (batch normalization and a ReLU followed by 3×3 convolution followed) and a fully connected layer with softmax preceded by an average pooling. To allow the training of multi-band satellite imagery the network is modified to accept an input of $224 \times 224 \times C$ where C is the number of channels of the image and the fully connected layer is adapted to do a regression instead of a classification.

Source: Author's Compilation

6.2 Feature Extraction

For each of the input band combinations (MS, NL), five separate models were trained using a 5-fold cross-validation procedure. To do so, the data was divided into 5 folds of roughly equal size (same number of clusters). See Table 3 to visualize the folds used for the training. Each model was then trained on 3-folds, validated on a 4th, and tested on a 5th. See Table 4 to visualize the splits used in the cross-validation procedure. Note that to help avoid spatial overlap among the training, validation and test divisions of each folder, the data was divided by municipality instead of individual census sectors.

Table 3. Folds used for training.

Fold	Municipalities	# census sectors
A	Eldorado, Pariquera-Açu, São Lourenço da Serra, Ilha Comprida, Sete Barras, Jacupiranga, Bocaiúva do Sul	181
B	Adrianópolis, Iporanga, Pedro Toledo, Tapiraí, Barra do Turvo, Tunas do Paraná, Barra do Chapéu, Itapirapuã Paulista, Itaóca, Ribeira, Doutor Ulysses, Cananéia	168
C	Juquitiba, Itaperuçu, Rio Branco do Sul, Cajati	180
D	Apiai, Iguape, Registro	179
E	Juquiá, Cerro Azul, Miracatu, Itariri	172

Source: Author's compilation.

Table 4. Split of the 5 folds used for all cross-validated training.

Model	Train	Val	Test
1	C, D, E	B	A
2	A, D, E	C	B
3	A, B, E	D	C
4	A, B, C	E	D
5	B, C, D	A	E

Source: Author's compilation.

The ResNet-18 models were trained with the Adam optimizer and MSE loss function. The batch size is 64 and the learning rate is decayed by a factor of 0.96 after each epoch. To improve the performance and ability of the model to generalize, data augmentation - random flips and random brightness/contrast on the MS images - and shuffling techniques were used.

The MS models were trained with 50 epochs and the NL models were trained with 150 epochs. In the original article, both MS and NL were trained with 200 epochs but that number was too high for Vale do Ribeira's dataset, leading to overfitting. Note that the validation loss is being used as a metric for early stopping: a checkpoint of the model was saved every time a lowest MSE was achieved, but specifically in the case of the MS models, the network trained very fast for all 5 models and sometimes the checkpoint saved was corresponding to a value of epoch

too high, even though the difference between the MSE's were very small. See Figure 7 for an example of overfitting in the training models when the number of epochs is equal to 200.

Figure 7: This model corresponds to the Model 4 in Table 4 when trained with the MS bands. The checkpoint saved was at the epoch 175, which is too high. At this checkpoint the model clearly is overfitted. Source: Author's compilation.

See Figures 8 and 9 for an illustration of the final training and validation loss of each model of the MS and NL bands, respectively.

Figure 8: Training and validation curves for MS models. The red lines represent the checkpoints where the model obtained the lowest MSE. Source: Author's Compilation.

Figure 9: Training and validation curves for NL models. The red lines represent the checkpoints where the model obtained the lowest MSE. Source: Author's Compilation.

6.3 Features Concatenation

After training the MS and NL models, their feature maps were extracted and saved as a compressed numpy .npz file. The feature maps contain the pertinent features to classify the images and, after being flattened, they serve as input for the fully connected layers. In the case of the ResNet18, the feature map of each image has a dimension of 1x1x512.

To form the combined MS + NL models, the MS and NL feature vectors are concatenated resulting in feature vectors of dimension 1024.

6.4 Ridge Regression

Once the combined feature vectors were obtained, the last fully connected layer of the models was fine-tuned using ridge regression with leave-one-group-out cross-validation.

The L2 norm regularization parameter alpha of the regression is chosen during the cross-validation procedure: the best alpha is the one that yields the lowest mean squared error (Figure 10).

Figure 10: Example of leave-one-group-out cross-validation means square errors / alpha. In this case, lowest MSE = 0.005 and best alpha = 16. Source: Author's compilation.

7. Results

7.1 Performance

To analyze the results, the principal metric chosen was the coefficient of determination (R^2). This coefficient is used to identify the strength of the model, it captures how well the predictions match the observations, or how much of the variation in the observed data is explained by the predictions. Usually the R^2 varies between 0 and 1, being expressed as a percentage (the closer to 1, the better). This metric is very used to measure the performance of a regression method due to its facility of interpretation, being usually more informative than error metrics that have arbitrary ranges, such as MSE.

To evaluate the performance in the same manner as Yeh et al. [1], the squared Pearson correlation coefficient (r^2), the Spearman's rank correlation coefficient (rank) and the MSE were also used. The r^2 is powerful to find patterns and relationships in data and the closer to 1, the higher the correlation between the variables. While the squared Pearson's correlation (r^2) assesses linear relationships, Spearman's rank correlation assesses monotonic relationships (whether linear or not). See Figure 11 to visualize the regression plot for the combined MS + NL model.

Figure 11: Regression plot for the combined MS+NL model. The dotted line corresponds to the line of best fit. Source: Author's compilation.

The coefficient of determination between the observed and predicted values was $R^2 = 0.289$. This value is very low when compared to the results obtained by Yeh et al. [1], but this can be justified taking in consideration the limited size of the dataset of Vale do Ribeira, which corresponds to approximately 4.4% of the dataset used in the African countries algorithm. The value also was lower than the R^2 found by Triñanes et al. [2] ($R^2 = 0.38$), but again the dataset is smaller, the training set of the model was done with only 15% of the size of the training set used by Triñanes et al. [2].

Another factor that might be leading to a low performance is that even though the data was splitted between municipalities to aggregate the closests census sectors and avoid overlapping between the images, there is still the possibility of overlapping between the folders, characterizing peeking in the training and leading to overfitting. A better approach would be dividing the census sectors using a DBSCAN algorithm to create folders in which the images don't overlap. Yeh et al. adopted the methodology of dividing the folders by countries, which they denominated out-of-country split, and also used the DBSCAN algorithm to create a second division, which they denominated in-country split. Nevertheless, for this project, with the images resolution of 30m/pixel and the CNN with input 224x224, it was not possible to apply this algorithm.

For comparison, I also ran the ridge regression for the separated MS and NL models, and redid the whole training procedure considering just the RGB bands. See the metrics results in the figure below.

	r2	R2	mse	rank
Resnet-18 MS+NL concat	0.294940	0.289370	0.004663	0.567761
Resnet-18 MS	0.285869	0.285763	0.004686	0.556179
Resnet-18 NL	0.230912	0.223876	0.005092	0.521667
Resnet-18 RGB	0.110392	0.109057	0.005846	0.298294

Figure 12: Final metrics results. Source: Author's compilation.

The CNN trained on the RGB bands performed poorly compared to the others models, which is expected and confirms the relevance of using multispectral daytime imagery and nightlight imagery when predicting socioeconomic data.

The CNNs trained only on NL or MS imagery performed similarly to each other and almost as well as the combined model MS+NL, suggesting that these two inputs contain similar

information, at least for the task of predicting spatial variation in Vale do Ribeira's income indicator. This affirmation can be reinforced by the heatmaps drawn in Figure 13, it is possible to visualize that the separated and the combined models have predictions with a high correlation (r^2 and rank).

Figure 13: Correlation results for the income predictions of all models a) comparison of r^2 metric and b) for rank metric . Source: Author's compilation.

7.2 Visual Analysis

To provide a visual aid of the results, heatmaps with the values of the real and estimated data were made (Figure 14 and 15).

Figure 14: Real IDH Income indicator for Vale do Ribeira. The colorbar corresponds to the real income values.. Source: Author's compilation.

Figure 15: Estimated IDH Income Vale do Ribeira. The colorbar corresponds to the estimated income values. Source: Author's compilation.

To complement this visual analysis, the difference between the real income score y and the predicted \hat{y} value, defined as $d = |y - \hat{y}|$, was also calculated and plotted in the heatmap (Figure 16). From this figure it is possible to visualize that a great part of the census sectors yield a small difference between the real and estimated values, for instance 44,66% of census sectors obtained d equal or lowest to 0.05.

Differences between the real and predicted labels for each census sector of Vale do Ribeira

Figure 16: Difference between the real and predicted labels for each census sector of vale do Ribeira. Source: Author's compilation.

8. Next Steps

Since the small size of the dataset used in this project proved to be prejudicial to the model performance, the next step is to adopt a different methodology for the collection of the images with the goal of increasing considerably the number of images to be used in the model. In this spirit, doing “random crops” when decreasing the size of the image to fit the input of the CNN can be used as a form of data augmentation. It is important to highlight the importance of a detailed analysis of the size of the images at the methodology adopted to adapt their resolution and avoid peeking in the test set.

Another interesting analysis is to predict the socioeconomic data for the municipalities instead of the census sectors. In an analogy, this approach was done by Yeh et al. in which the authors concluded that aggregating predictions and ground measurements to the district level further improves performance, with predictions explaining on average 83% of the ground measurements in held-out countries not used to train the model.

Finally, updating the study with the 2021 census (when available) can be very interesting. It opens the margin to use the Sentinel-2 satellite for the daytime imagery collection. Sentinel-2 has 10m resolution and when compared with 30m Landsat resolution can yield better results.

9. Conclusions

In this report, public satellite imagery was used to train a combined CNN model to estimate socioeconomic data over space in the Vale do Ribeira region. The model yields a low performance when compared to the one of Yeh et al. [1], which attempts to replicate. Nevertheless, it is still promising once the dataset employed was considerably smaller than the one used in the original study (it corresponds to only 4.4% of the size of the dataset used by Yeh et al.).

It is also interesting to highlight that even though $R^2 = 0.289$, almost 45% of the difference between the values of the real and predicted labels were less than 0.05, reinforcing the potential of the model. Furthermore, the CNNs trained only on NL or MS imagery performed similarly to each other and almost as well as the combined model MS+NL, suggesting that these two inputs contain similar information, at least for the task of predicting spatial variation in Vale do Ribeira's income indicator. This is a very interesting result that also was obtained by Yeh et al. in the task of predicting spatial variation in the African countries.

The original study of Yeh et al. [1] was difficult to replicate since the author constructed several other models and adopted different methodologies to prove/compare the efficacy of its results. Therefore, the code available and the article were dense and, honestly, sometimes difficult to summarize and understand. Once this algorithm is now summarized and clean, it gets easier to focus on improving the performance of the model. The next step in attempting to improve such performance is to adopt a different methodology for the collection of the images, focusing on increasing considerably the number of images to be used in the model.

In conclusion, using satellite imagery to develop an inexpensive and scalable deep learning method for estimating socioeconomic indicators to fill the 10-years data gap in Brazil is very promising, and although this study did not yield a good performance at the moment, it is a step towards understanding how convolutional neural networks, multispectral daytime imagery and nighttime imagery can be used to this end.

10. References

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